

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding – Call 1

Progress Report

Project	
Project number	24-CoARA-045
Name of the project	Impact-based assessment of the translational research in the Italian research hospitals
Type of project	<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional change x <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional pilot
Reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> M0 – M6 <input type="checkbox"/> M7 – M12
Reporting deadline	June 25th, 2025
Date of last update of the report	June 25th, 2025

Organisation	
Organisation name Please fill-in information in red for Teaming Project's coordinator	Contact Name, mail address
Associazione Ricercatori in Sanità – Italia (ARSI)	Valeria Elisa Contarino, valeria.contarino@gmail.com

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1. Purpose of the CoARA Cascade Funding Progress Report

The CoARA Cascade Funding Progress Report serves as a tool for supporting beneficiaries of the program in sharing progress with the CoARA Secretariat, and, upon request, the European Commission. It provides a framework to track progress, monitor activities, and bring transparency in how resources are used during the reporting period.

Additionally, the template facilitates continual reflection and documentation of the projects, allowing for a comprehensive overview of their activities, achievements.

For Teaming projects, please note that one Progress Report is expected per project.

Please note that this monitoring report template covers the technical aspect of the progress reporting and that the Excel table “Project Budget template” covers the financial part. Please fill in the Excel table according to your type of project:

- Annex 4 - for mono-beneficiary (i.e., Institutional Pilot Calls and Institutional Change Calls):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-unique-partner-1.xlsx>

OR

- Annex 5 - for partnering projects (i.e., Teaming Calls – each partner must complete one sheet in the document):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-partnering-projects-1.xlsx>

Both documents are mandatory and expected to be submitted to complete the reporting milestones in M06 and M12.

Please send back your report, your use of resources (Excel budget table) and your annexes (if applicable) by June 25th, 2025, to secretariat@coara.eu

2. Monitoring system

To ensure easy monitoring of the progress made in the funded projects, the monitoring system consists of the following parts:

- Progress measurement base (section 2.1.)
- Progress reporting (section 2.2.)
- Dissemination activities (section 2.3)
- Next Steps (section 2.4)
- Budget Monitoring (section 2.5)

2.1. Progress measurement base: Work plan

Please provide a hyperlink or summary of your work plan for the **M0 – M6 period** in the box below.

The M0 – M6 workplan defined at the beginning of the project was the following:

- engagement of researchers at all career stages working in the Italian Istituti di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) research hospitals through ARSI mailing-list, social media (LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook) and open online calls;
- kick-off meeting by the end of the first trimester (milestones 1, deliverable 1: detailed plan activities and report);
- online trainings about the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM), model and toolkit <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu/>

2.2. Progress reporting

This section aims to facilitate reporting of progress for all projects, and coordination of partners for Teaming projects.

2.2.1. Reporting process

The table and text boxes below provide a simplified method to report on projects' progress quantitatively and qualitatively. Please add as many rows as required.

Outputs/ Deliverables/ Activity	Brief description	Its relevance to <u>ARRA</u> <u>commitments</u> Which commitment is addressed and how?	Hyperlin k to final version if available	Timefram e MM/YY	Funding acknowledgemen t (if available)
Engagemen t	Engagemen t of different stakeholder s in the IRCCS ecosystem	1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 6.2 Develop criteria/tools with researchers involved 7. Raise awareness and provide training The engagement of researchers and other professionals at all career stages across IRCCS aims to involve those affected by		01/-03/25	

		<p>research assessment. This supports inclusiveness and participatory development of new assessment approaches based on impact, in line with commitments 1, 6.2, and 7.</p>			
Kick-off meeting	Open meeting with different IRCCS stakeholders	<p>7. Raise awareness and provide transparent communication</p> <p>The kick-off meeting introduced the rationale and goals of the project to stakeholders and created a space for open discussion on research assessment. It helped raise awareness and shared preliminary strategies for implementation.</p>		03/25	

Report	Report of the kick-off meeting	<p>7. Raise awareness and provide transparent communication</p> <p>We decided to provide a link to the report in order to sensibelize on the topic of finding alternatives to the current state of art of the research assessment in the IRCCS accessible to everyone.</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/15723907?token=eyJhbGciOiJIUzUxMiJ9.eyJpZCI6ImJlYmY0YTNiLTZhODYtNGY2Zi04MDE4LWVRkNzY3ZDQyYWFkMCI6ImRhdGEiOnt9LCJyYW5kb20iOiJiNTRIYTQ3M2E1MGUxMmZiNjY5ZjQ0NDQ5OTQ3NjhmNCJ9.4hnlc-_W2hQ8_Ob_ncmEnNHNPoiRT8ttAjV9SmpHdRvY2EYT5aK60eGtTL-1okk8RBNZe5g2rmJbCE</p>	03/25	
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n. IRCCS professionals trained = 106	Number of IRCCS workers trained on the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) framework and toolkit	<p>2. Base research assessment on qualitative evaluation</p> <p>3. Abandon inappropriate use of metrics</p> <p>7. Provide training on assessment criteria</p> <p>Training researchers in the use of the TSBM model promotes qualitative, context-sensitive assessment approaches and moves away from reliance on metrics like JIF or h-index, aligned with commitments 2, 3, and 7.</p>		04-06/25	
n. Post training surveys collected= 46	Surveys for the participants to the training about the Translational	<p>1. Recognise the diversity of contributions</p> <p>6.2 Develop criteria/tools with</p>		04-06/25	

	<p>Science Benefits Model (TSBM) framework and toolkit</p>	<p>researchers involved</p> <p>The training was open to all professional roles working in the IRCCS ecosystem. Thus, the post training surveys allowed us to collect feedback from diverse profiles, ensuring that the proposal developed will be inclusive and reflect the real needs of researchers and other staff.</p>			
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Please make sure that funding acknowledgement is added to all your publications.

Please link your publications/outputs in the following Zenodo community [“CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Beneficiaries”](#). For support, please refer to the guidelines in Annex 1.

Please use the following title format to name your documents: “CoARA Boost CFI – [Acronym of the project/3 first words of your project title] – [Document title]”

Example (fictive): CoARA Boost CFI – COSMOS – Booklet for Strategic Meeting”

2.2.2. Narrative assessment of progress

Period 1 - reporting deadline: June 25th, 2025

The narrative assessment of progress should detail current progress, including successes and hurdles encountered during implementation of the workplan.

If your project is organised in WPs, please mention the title and give a summary of work/tasks conducted in each.

Please detail your progress' narrative assessment in the box below.

M0-M3

During the first three months, the activities focused on stakeholders engagement, preparation of the training sessions, preparation of the surveys, and organization of the kick-off meeting.

The stakeholders involved included:

- Researchers and other professionals (e.g., staff from grant offices, librarians, etc) working in the IRCCS
- Scientific Directors in the IRCCS
- The Director of the Research and Innovation Unit at the Italian Ministry of Health

In addition to strengthening the national network, we engaged in international exchanges by participating in both in-person and online initiatives focused on the real-world impact of research across the EU, UK, and US.

The open kick-off meeting was held in a hybrid format, with an in-person event in Milan (the Italian city with the highest number of IRCCS researchers) and remote participation available. The chair of the CoARA Italian chapter participated as speaker together with the Vicepresident of the Association and the coordinator of the present project. A total of 86 individuals attended the meeting: 32 in person and 54 remotely. A detailed report of the kick-off meeting is available.

Two surveys were developed to collect data after the TSBM training and after the practical application of the TSBM toolkit on the projects.

M4-M6

In the second quarter, the activities were focused on delivering training sessions within the IRCCS network and collecting data through the surveys. Five different IRCCS institutions were engaged: four public and one private, three in Milano and two in Rome.

The training sessions were adapted to the specific needs of the participating groups and institutions, and varied in terms of:

- Format: in-person or online
- Duration: from 1 to 3 hours
- Structure: combined explanation and practical application in the same session, or split into separate sessions
- Audience: single research group, multiple research groups, or institutional-level sessions

A total of 106 professionals were trained across the different IRCCS institutions. Thus, the first KPI=100 trainings was achieved.

A total of 46 surveys were collected after the training.

2.3. Dissemination activities

Include in this section where your project information was disseminated or if outputs achieve impact.

Please add as many rows as required.

Name Please specify the type of activity (e.g. webinar, presentations' slides, ...)	Link	Target audience
E-mails to the ARSI mailing list to inform about the project and invite to the kick-off meeting		Researchers and other professionals (e.g., staff from grant offices, librarians, etc) working in the Istituti di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS)
Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn posts/stories to inform about the project and invite to the kick-off meeting		Researchers and other professionals (e.g., staff from grant offices, librarians, etc) working in the Istituti di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS)
Meeting to inform about the project and invite to the kick-off meeting		The Director of the Research and Innovation Unit at the Italian Ministry of Health
Email with attached project summary and invitation to the kick-off meeting		Scientific Directors of the IRCCS
Presentation at the ARSI annual meeting to report on the kick-off meeting and project activities		Researchers and other professionals (e.g., staff from grant offices, librarians, etc) working in the Istituti di Ricovero e

		Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS)
Online TV interview to disseminate about the starting of the project		Italian population
Press interview		Italian population
Meeting to report on the kick-off meeting and project activities		Scientific Director

2.4. Next steps

The “next steps” section should detail future actions, including activities and decisions, to be taken and/or implemented to achieve the project.

Please describe the **future action and activities planned for the M7 – M12 period** in the box below.

- Complete the collection of real-world data on the IRCCS context through the surveys on the training participants in the IRCCS (milestone 3, KPI= 50 surveys);
- Support to the research groups to apply the TSBM framework on real-world projects;
- Collection of data through a second survey to the groups that apply the TSBM on IRCCS projects and relative collection of benefits and metrics;
- Analysis of the data collected through the surveys;
- In-person wrap-up meeting (milestone 4, deliverable 2: report and position paper) to disseminate the results of the project and discuss the scale-up and sustainability of the adoption of qualitative impact-based criteria in the evaluation assessment of the translational research with representatives of the Italian Ministry of Health.

2.5. Budget monitoring

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Annex 1 – Guidelines for CoARA signatories on uploading outputs files to the CoARA community on Zenodo

Step 1: Accessing Zenodo

Go to the Zenodo website: <https://zenodo.org/>

Sign in to your Zenodo account using your credentials. If you do not have an account, you can create one by following the registration process.

Step 2: Uploading Your Outputs/Publications

From your Zenodo dashboard, click on the "Upload" button. Choose "Publication" from the content types.

1. **Select the output/publication file** from your computer that you wish to upload. Ensure that your file is in an appropriate format (e.g., PDF, Word document).
2. **Fill in the required metadata**, including title, authors, description, and keywords. Please ensure that you mention "CoARA" in the keywords for easy identification.
3. **For the "DOI,"** you can choose to either:
 - Leave it blank if you don't have a specific DOI in mind and click "Reserve DOI" if you would like one to be auto-generated for this submission.
 - If you have a DOI that you would like to associate with this submission, enter it in the provided field.
4. **Under "Communities," select "CoARA Boost Cascade Funding beneficiaries"** to associate your upload with our community.
5. **Review the licensing options** and select the one that aligns with your preferences for sharing and reuse.
6. **Click Save and Publish** to submit your file.

Step 3: Notify CoARA Secretariat

Please send an email to secretariat@coara.eu once you have uploaded your output/publication. Include the title and DOI of your upload for easy reference.

Note: If you have multiple versions of the output/publication, we kindly ask you to create a new version on Zenodo rather than uploading separate files.